

2-TOM, 2-SON

COMPARATIVE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT METHODS OF TYPE 1 AND
2 DIABETES

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Abstract. In this article, the causes and complications of diabetes mellitus and its 1st and 2nd types are described in detail, and the comparative diagnosis of these two types is written.

Key words: diabetes, diagnosis, analysis, diagnosis, treatment, initial symptoms, etc.

Diabetes mellitus (lat. diabetes mellitus, "sugar disease") is a group of endocrine diseases associated with impaired glucose absorption and resulting in a relative or absolute deficiency of the insulin hormone. As a result of this, hyperglycemia is observed - a steady increase in the amount of sugar in the blood. The disease is characterized by chronic delay, as well as carbohydrate, fat, protein, mineral and water-salt metabolism disorders. Diabetes is the most common chronic disease in developed countries today. The number of such patients is increasing every year in all countries of the world. Diabetic patients are mainly bothered by symptoms such as thirst, frequent urination, weight loss, lack of appetite, and fatigue. Patients with the above-mentioned complaints should be examined by an endocrinologist immediately. In modern medicine, the severity of the disease and the presence or absence of complications are taken into account when choosing drugs. For example, if the patient lacks insulin due to heredity at a young age, insulin is sent to replace it. Elderly and overweight people need to follow a diet according to the doctor's recommendation when there is a relative lack of insulin. Blood sugar lowering agents are used. A diet is often prescribed when the disease subsides. Carbohydrates are consumed less, instead of them you can eat meat, black bread and other products. The amount of fatty foods is limited.

2-TOM, 2-SON

When the disease worsens, the patient is not given butter and other fatty products. Almost 20 percent of food calories should consist of proteins. Food products consumed by a sick person should be rich in vitamins, especially vitamins of group C and B. The patient should eat food in portions. Patients who follow the doctor's strict supervision must strictly follow the recommendations regarding the daily routine and diet, and must come to the laboratory examination on time. Today, diabetes is considered a natural disease. According to experts of the World Health Organization, diabetes is a metabolic disorder. It is caused by observation of an irreversible condition in a certain part of the pancreas. The pancreas is located behind the stomach, in front of the 1st, 2nd lumbar vertebrae. Length 10-15 cm, thickness 2-3 cm, weight 70-100 grams. The pancreas consists of 3 parts: head, body, tail. The main part of the pancreas is the exocrine secretory apparatus, which mainly produces the main parts of the pancreatic juice. 1-3% of the gland is the endocrine part, that is, islets of Langerhans (up to 1-1.5 million). The diameter of each is 150 μm . There are 80 to 200 cells in one islet. There are several types of cells in the islets of Langerhans: A - glucagon makes up 25%; B - located in the center of insulin, makes up 60-70%; D - somatostatin makes up 10%, the rest makes up 5% and produces VIP (Visoactive interstitial polypeptide, gastrointerstitial polypeptide). Insulin is a highly active chemical substance (hormone) that accumulates and is grouped into islets. A person uses energy to live, move and work. It gets energy from food. Energy is produced as a result of metabolism. Carbohydrates and fats are the main source of energy. Bread, cereals, dairy products, fruits and vegetables contain a lot of carbohydrates. A part of the glucose entered through food is absorbed into the cells with the help of insulin. Insulin can be compared to a key that opens a cell lock. Part of the glucose used for energy production is converted into glycogen with the help of insulin and is stored in the liver and muscles as an energy reserve.

As a result of severe stress, a lot of stress, severe fear, these cells can be blocked and cannot be restored. As a result, insulin release decreases. This leads to an increase in the amount of sugar in the blood. The normal amount of sugar in the blood of a healthy person is 80-120 mg%. In case of diabetes, its amount can increase to 150-250 mg% and even more. When the amount of sugar in the blood is normal, it is not excreted through the kidneys with urine, that is, there is absolutely no sugar in the urine of a healthy person. When the amount of sugar in the blood exceeds 140 - 150 mg%, it starts to be excreted in the urine. At such a time, a person becomes thirsty quickly and consumes a lot of water. Carbohydrates in the eaten food are not absorbed by the cells and tissues, but are excreted in the urine. Otherwise, the fat reserves under the skin will break down and turn into glucose, and even the protein and fat substances in the cells and tissues will turn into glucose, pass into the blood and be

2-TOM, 2-SON

excreted with urine. As a result, the patient becomes weak, weak, and the ability to work decreases. Diabetes occurs in 15% of the population of our republic, they regularly eat diet food and drink drugs that reduce the amount of sugar in the blood. Regardless of the medications taken, a person with diabetes should follow a diet, follow a healthy lifestyle, give up harmful habits, engage in light physical work or physical education, observe personal hygiene, take care of himself. In order to be able to choose a profession, and most importantly, to receive reasonable treatment, to maintain his ability to work and health for a long time, he should have medical knowledge and culture about this disease. High blood sugar can lead to serious complications, which can sometimes take years to appear. These complications are called late complications and they damage vital organs such as eyes, nerves, kidneys, and blood vessels. Sometimes a late complication can be detected even in diabetes that is detected for the first time. Only normalization of blood sugar can prevent the development of late complications of diabetes. To determine the presence of complications of diabetes, it is necessary to undergo a full examination.

For this reason, body weight at the age of 25 was accepted as normal weight. Everyone should be able to maintain the weight of this age until the end of life. The pancreas, which is already adapted to deliver insulin to the weight of this age, naturally cannot deliver more than this. As a result, sugar metabolism goes out of control. Due to the lack of insulin, excess sugar that is not used or absorbed by the body accumulates in the blood. The amount of sugar in the blood increases and exceeds its normal limit and begins to be excreted through urine. The more sugar accumulates in the blood, the more water you drink and the more you urinate. Thus, the main symptoms of diabetes are known as drinking a lot of water (thirst) and urinating a lot. At the same time, poor absorption of sugar by the body due to low production or lack of insulin also causes the patient to feel hungry. But the patient cannot eat a lot of food, because the food cannot be digested due to the lack of insulin, the patient begins to lose weight. It is clear that all symptoms of diabetes mellitus are interconnected and mediated by a single pathophysiological chain. This chronic, long-lasting disease damages important organs, tissues and blood vessels and shows them its complications. First of all, this is seen in the activity of the nervous system. Limbs ache, ache or heat up. The perception of pain decreases, a complication of the disease called polyneuropathy develops. It destroys the kidney function, as a result, the kidneys are unable to perform their tasks. Eyesight decreases, as a result of a decrease in the body's immune system, purulent wounds on the skin, serious diseases (painless myocardial infarction, etc.), and blackheads develop on the legs. As you can see, diabetes is dangerous with its complications.

2-TOM, 2-SON

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